

The Structure of the Atomic Nucleus, Force and the Role of Neutrinos.

Abstract

The fundamental structure of atomic nuclei is currently unknown despite many theories concerning nuclear particles and how they may function. The new Rotation-space-Time (RST) causal theory of the universe should and does provide a fundamental structure of nuclei. This article extracts the main steps expressed in that theory producing both atoms and their nuclear structures. This requires details of the structures of the main sub-atomic particles, their motion, energy, and particularly force – all given in the RST approach. The action of force follows directly from the cause of the universe via Einstein's energy quanta, or photons. These in turn depend upon a three-dimensional special relativistic rotation, not to be confused with Dirac spin matrices. During construction under stellar pressure this action automatically causes the protons to be arranged around neutron rings in such a way that the proton force fields do not interfere with each other. This requires the intercession of neutrinos which fill a major but completely unexpected role in nuclear construction. The various arrangements decide the atomic (elemental) properties as the number of nucleons increases creating a series of properties similar to those of Mendeleev's table.

Keywords: atomic nuclei, neutrinos, force fields, particle structure.

1.1 Introduction

To understand the structure of atomic nuclei it is first necessary to understand the fundamental structure of the particles that form atoms, their force fields and how this affects their interactions. This is fully described in Thompson (2023, 2024a,b) and summarized below.

The basis for this structure is the premise that the existence of the universe must follow from a single first cause, Time (defined §1.2). This automatically produces a three-dimensional rotating space-Time (RST) based on units defined as quantum units of length and time: quls and quts (§1.2).^{1,2} A Universe can be constructed solely from this basis under the principle that the Universe requires no knowledge of any specific measurements and is therefore totally non-mathematical. Thus all deductions are made by non-mathematical logic – incorporating explanations of human observations. RST provides an over-arching rule that the entire Universe and its basic elements have to obey (§1.2). This leads directly to the existence of particles which have identical properties to those observed by humans for neutrons, protons, electrons, photons and neutrinos.³ However, these are not necessarily formed in line with human theories. For example, an important difference arises over 'mass': in human theory mass causes a resistance to motion whereas in the RST picture particles automatically have a resistance to motion giving the human impression of mass. Testing of the picture, by introducing measurement, mathematically produces an equation of

¹ I use capitals for Time and Universe to distinguish their usage as defined from my definition of time as the results may considerably differ from ideas other people may have.

² The rotation mentioned must not be confused with the Goudsmit-Uhlenbeck/Dirac quantum spin (statistics) which has nothing whatsoever to do with the rotation introduced here.

³ i.e. explaining completely the nature and surprising actions of the neutrino which until this new Time picture of the Universe were unknown. (Other odd particles such as muons, anti-particles, Higgs and resonances are also naturally accounted for).

motion which all particles obey (Thompson 2024a:ch11). This gives minimum velocities for the three fundamental particles: the electron minimum velocity is $8.376088 \times 10^{-8}c$ which is 1836.18537 times faster than that of the proton. The proton automatically has a minimum velocity about 1.0014 times that of the neutron. These are very close to, but not exactly in line with CODATA values as the latter are obtained by human experiment on Earth which travels through the universe and thus has an unknowable relativistic content (Thompson 2024a:ch11).⁴ The RST values relate to the centre of rotation of the Universe.

However, the most important deduction is an exact description of the mechanics of force. It is fundamental to understanding how nuclear particles are arranged so that they do not interfere with each other (§2.5). The human concept of charge is extraneous; that is, the action of force between particles automatically follows from the Universal rule without any reference to a so-called electromagnetic charge. It is not continuous but directional (see§2.6) allowing protons to be in close proximity without interacting. Their satisfactory arrangement, however, requires the action of another particle, the neutrino, the actions of which are hidden from mathematics (§3.2).

1.2 Definition of Time – Fundamental cause

Time is defined in Thompson (2023§3.4) as

Time is a self-generated ordered progression of recordable points all with the same form but such that each point is distinct from any other.

where

- *Self-generated* implies some operation, or fundamental action, \hat{T} , by which time creates new points in the progression. The form of this operation explains the most fundamental processes of the universe.
- *Ordered progression* here means the orderly operation of \hat{T} , so that a point produced in the first instant, or stage, of the progression can be called, in human perception, the first point and assigned the ‘number one’.⁵ The point, or points (the possibility of more than one depends on the determination of \hat{T}) generated in the second instant (stage) belong to the second place in the progression and so on. Points are then produced in sequence allowing the progression to have sub-sequences of stages, each consisting of a string of single stages in order, starting with a first stage, second stage, et cetera, in a particular subsequence where each point in the subsequence corresponds to a position in the overall progression (see Figures 1.2, 1.3). The action/form of \hat{T} must include the cause for this progression. Points cannot be divided because there can be nothing smaller; if splitting were possible the progression would not be well defined.
- In terms of semantics, by point I have to use the words ‘it is dimensionless’, it has ‘no size’* Its complete form has to be determined and this will depend on the form of \hat{T} .

⁴Everything in the universe travels w.r.t the original starting point of the universe. But the original point travels w.r.t all other points so cannot be recognized.

⁵ Bearing in mind the Universe does not enumerate!.

- Recordable. The dictionary definition is “to put in some permanent form; keep for remembrance”. The concept that a point is recordable must follow from the form of the points. (Thompson 2023:§4.6)
- The distinctness principle depends on the form of the points.

* Size in the absence of space or volume in the cause, needs description. It is part of our perceptions because we can reach out and touch objects and look through telescopes at ‘distant’ objects from which we infer the existence of space and volume. But this does not determine the nature of space. Its existence must follow from the above cause. The useless statement “it just is” must be censured.

Thus:

The fundamental action of the Universe is one that creates a self-generated ordered progression of recordable points all of the same form but such that each point is distinct from any other.

Thompson (2023:§4.3-4.6, 2024a) show how this definition develops first, an interval of time (qt), and then how this produces an interval of space (qt) in human view. The result is obtained through the introduction of rotation, not to be confused with Dirac’s spin. This rotation has to arise in three orthogonal directions implying \hat{T} must be implemented via three spinning points carrying Time, \mathfrak{S} s, so producing the human concept of a spatial interval (Figure 1.1). Two universes then exist: a **natural Universe** which has no size but has two balancing contra-rotating spins ($\dot{\theta}^+$ and $\dot{\theta}^-$) which (2023§4.5) can be regarded as $\dot{\theta}^+$ existing inside $\dot{\theta}^-$ to create a recognizable (by living creatures) internal relativistic space,⁶ a **relativistic Universe**, such that the **total space and spatial intervals always have a tangential velocity of c** .⁷ The equivalent rotation (angular velocity) for the first point of Time is defined as w though the Universe has no need of having any value for this ‘quantity’. w is therefore a maximum possible rotation for the Universe that automatically gives a tangential velocity of c to a point of Time.

Figure 1.1 The expansion of Time to form a Time interval, which also creates the human concept of space, and thus space-Time as derived in Thompson (2023§4.4). RST produces a tetragonal structure which, if humans imagine it as rotating, has the appearance of a cone spinning around an axis through

⁶ The result is the fore-runner leading to the natural action which Einstein recognized in his 1905 special theory, cf Thompson (2023:§4.8)

⁷ c originally was merely a constant but is later shown to be the same as the speed of light.

its apex perpendicular to its base. The \mathfrak{S} s represent spinning points of Time generated by \hat{T} . They **materialize** at P1,2,3/ABC to leave *recordable trace-points*, then immediately move on to materialize at the next stage creating further trace-points. The \mathfrak{S} s *only* arise at the points of the tetrahedron as if they had jumped instantaneously from the origin carrying the rotation with them. The tetrahedron is therefore only an instantaneous materialization though it ‘carries’ a rotation, but, as in (2023§4.4), it creates the relativistic appearance of space.

This gives the following general rule.

The \mathfrak{S} s creating space-Time must travel along three rotating orthogonal axes such that they (\mathfrak{S} s) maintain the same distance from their originating point as the distance between them; they must travel at c^ ; and remain distinct (Thompson 2023:§4.11);*

where the \mathfrak{S} s are the ‘bearers of Time’. This rule defines the **constraints** of the Time system, that is, they define the rule that every fundamental RST object in the Universe has to obey. They determine what can, and cannot, follow from the original premise.

1.3 Expanding space-Time

Following from the general rule, \hat{T} automatically continues to generate further space-Time intervals from each previous interval in ordered progression. This induces the principle of a network, or **lattice**, of identical trace-points built up tetragonally, the first three stages of which are drawn in three equivalent imaginary forms in Figure 1.2. The lattice in the *natural* representation, has no volume. Nevertheless, it would appear 3-dimensional in the human sense (2023§4.4) that the points are arranged in lattice form with no distance between them. Through the action of \hat{T} , every new space-Time module generated in the development of the lattice, starts with the same conditions as every other, consequently avoiding any ‘addition of velocities’ problem.

In both the natural or relativistic representation the result is the same: when the first generation (first cut) of space-Time points materializes, it is the \mathfrak{S} s that materialize. Each generates a new Time-point for the second generation in the progression leaving behind a trace-point (2023§4.3). When these \mathfrak{S} s of the second generation materialize they, too, leave behind trace-points, and so on as the progression advances. In the natural representation there would be no space between the points, and no measurable time interval although the points would still be generated in sequence; obviously such a diagram cannot be drawn.

Figure 1.2. Space-Time generation extending Figure 1.1b,c. to a second generation in diagrams (a) and (b) and a third generation in (c); (a) and (b) drawn in relief and (c) in plan view starting from the first cut – heavily lined, the second – medium lined the third – light. The cones and triads are just different representative methods of drawing the process of space-Time (trace-point) formation, (a) representing the human view of the \mathfrak{S} s spiralling and (b) jumping to form the trace-points. The tips of the arrows represent the final positions of the triad axes at the end of each cut and thus the position of the points forming a grid or lattice. In all three diagrams the first generation produces three new triads in the second generation. The axes of these second-generation triads meet at the points designated A, B and C which causes interference in space-Time production at these points. The outer three points P, Q, R continue normal production of a space-Time lattice as in diagram (c). The lines connecting the arrow tips to the triad origins are imaginary to show the direction of motion, or jump, of the relevant \mathfrak{S} s in human view. Note that although (a) appears to show the cones intersecting this is not the case as the \mathfrak{S} s jump directly and only appear at the base of the tetrahedra. (a) is of interest as it represents a possible representation in human view for a mathematical representation. (It shows the danger in the sole use of mathematics to formulate a universe.) (b) and (c) also show points of contact at positions A, B, C , see Figure 1.3.

Figure 1.3 (a) Four generations of space-Time in plan view extending from the black triad for the first stage to red at the fourth. When any *two* axes meet, unstable proto-particles form leaving a single (**free**) axis (sample shown as green-dotted arrows) to emerge from these coincidences (2023§4.7). These can, as in the blue ring, all direct (though not necessarily) internally, (cf §1.4 triple-triad). (b) The red triads form a larger (heart-shaped) ring with five possible internal coincidences e.g. from S and Q.

These coincidences of two points are an automatic effect of the creation of space-Time intervals. If both of the coinciding points were to generate space-Time intervals it would seem the expansion of each point would pass into the expansion of the other because the rotation generator has to act on both instantaneously. Expansion of the coincidences does not allow intersection so instead (2024a:§5.3.1) it produces a joint expansion as drawn in Figure 1.4.

1.4 Double triads

Figure 1.4. Reorientation of coincident triads from a possible uniqueness violating overlap in diagram (a) to a ‘double-triad’ in diagram (c). $\sim x: z \rightarrow y$ reads: rotating about the x -axis, the z -axis goes to the original y position shown by the dashed arrows. In the lower line, the red diagrams represent two rotations, first about the x -axis and then about the new position of the y -axis, from the original position. Diagram (c) shows the combined triads after all the rotations have been made; all six axial positions have been utilized once maintaining the orthogonality of the \mathfrak{T} s to each other to form a double-triad. These changes of orientation take place before the axes expand to the positions shown. Expansions about other axes are similar so that the Figure describes the general form. In the natural representation the complete action would be instantaneous. *Note that one axis (black x) has not changed its position. It is thus **free** to develop outside of the triad space in the next cut. The others cannot develop orthogonally outside as they would contain an additional spin of w orthogonal to their exterior development (cf Figure 1.5).* (d) shows the trace-points as they would appear in the relativistic representation at the formation of the third stage with gaps between them allowing the reorientated triads to form between them. The green arrows represent possible formation axes for the next section’s triple-triad.

This process automatically produces an important reaction (2024§5.3.1). As with all Time-points, the \mathfrak{T} s forming the double-triad on materialization produce a new generation of \mathfrak{T} s but those created from the double-triad carry the reorientation spin causing them to only develop in only one direction (addition of rotations would be greater than w). They are thus pure spinning points, **trions**, described in section 2.2.

Figure 1.5. Restricted Ξ emission. Taking the top reorientation in (b) the y -axis gains a rotation in the ik plane as the natural rotation takes y round in the next expansion thus ending with the direction shown. So the ik and ij planes are compromised by carrying the reorientation spin, w , leaving only the direction in the jk plane available for development from the y -axis.

1.5. Triple-triad

The triple-triad is formed from a combination of three double-triads as in Figure 1.6b,c.

Figure 1.6 Formation of a triple coincidence. The chance that all three free axes from A,B,C will meet as in diagram 1.6(b) is $1/27$. With three Ξ s involved in such a coincidence, the expectation would be the formation of three space-Time triads as they regenerate, but similarly to the double-triad, these triads cannot overlap. Therefore, they must automatically reorient into a free space as with the double-coincidence.

Figure 1.7. Reorientation of three coincident triads. The original directions lie superimposed on each other as in diagram (a). The rotations are made in the $\dot{\theta}^+$ direction (as seen from above). The central part of the Figure shows the individual triads rotated about one of their axes. The final diagram (b) shows the central parts superimposed. Note that the unchanged axes $1x, 2y, 3z$, in diagram (b) are drawn extended for recognition purposes but for each of these axes the reorientation process takes precedence to the expansion of the triads thus blocking these \mathfrak{T} s development – they become **suppressed** at the origin. The reorienting \mathfrak{T} s take up all the available paths (the axes along which the \mathfrak{T} s travel/jump to form the new space-Time building block). The result is shown in Figures 1.7b and 1.8b. As the human idea of zero at the origin of the triad does not exist, the suppressed \mathfrak{T} s would not intersect the space-Time axes or each other. They can thus form part of the total structure which appears as three triads, designated a **triple-triad**, even though the apparent form is that of two **super-triads**, named for ease of distinguishing between the two concepts.

This action, as with the double-triad, is an automatic response to the principles involved in the rotational action of the Time generator. That is, if the first cause of the prospective Universe is as given in the definition of Time – creation of rotating Time points that cannot intersect each other – the ‘automatic response’ (reorientation plus suppression) *must* take place.

Figure 1.8 The arrangement of the triple-triad axes, shown in the exploded diagram (a). The initial motion of the \mathfrak{T} s (in human imagery) is represented by the three cones with their triad axes (broken arrows) all spinning in the $\dot{\theta}^+$ direction (plain arrows). In (b) only the expanding \mathfrak{T} 's axes are given, grouped arbitrarily into ‘top’ and ‘bottom’ sets which would have to rotate according to their own $\dot{\theta}^+$ directions as shown. The third axes of each triad still exist, but their \mathfrak{T} s are trapped (suppressed)

at their origin. The labels x, y, z and their colours are for convenience of showing action only; there is no *natural* distinction between the \mathfrak{T} s represented by the axes.

This leads to another problem: the question of a rotational clash between the three triads. For example, Thompson (2023:§4.4-4.5) deduced that all pairs of neighbouring \mathfrak{T} s *must* meet the equidistant constraint – bearing in mind that all basic \mathfrak{T} s (ones not containing an additional orientation spin) are identical and thus cannot be distinguished from each other. However, inspection of Figure 1.8 shows that this equidistant requirement could only occur at the instant the triple-triad is formed.

Figure 1.8(a) shows the rotations of the axes of each of the three triads making up the two super- triads. Transferring the rotations of the axes to the super-triads as in Figure 1.8b shows that the top triad would have to rotate in the opposite direction to the bottom (the arrows show the differing directions of motion). Consequently, because the jumps between each subsequent materialization do not fit a full rotation, the \mathfrak{T} 's relative distances would be continually changing, breaking the fundamental rule that they must all be equidistant from each other.

The foundational principle automatically ‘proacts’ (cf 2024a:§4.5) as the rotation generator functions over both $\dot{\theta}^+$ and $\dot{\theta}^-$ rotations. Suppose that the lower super-triad in Figure 1.8b has $\dot{\theta}^+$ rotation, then the top super-triad is rotating in the opposite direction, as seen from the lower. To match the $\dot{\theta}^+$ rotation of the lower axes, the top-rotation at materialization of the \mathfrak{T} s must gain a *relative* rotation of double that value (*in human perception*) in the opposite direction: an apparent **synchronizing** rotation of twice the $\dot{\theta}^-$ spin so that the top triad rotates at the same rate as the bottom in the same direction when viewed from below (or above). The \mathfrak{T} s will then remain equidistant from each other.

Twice the $\dot{\theta}^-$ spin may seem to conflict with the maximum possible rotation magnitude, w , but this is not the case as the actual rotation of the top triad is the same as the bottom (w). Both still have a tangential velocity of c , but now in the same direction. Twice the $\dot{\theta}^-$ spin is purely a human rationalization to make mathematical sense of what the Universe does naturally to produce a legitimate result – showing the hidden fallibility of mathematics.

The foundational rule requires the synchronizing spin to be caused and regenerated every qut; which is equivalent to saying it must exist in space-Time, as nothing else but the original foundational cause exists. It must then exist in terms of \mathfrak{T} s which are part of the triple-triad itself. They rotate in the $\dot{\theta}^-$ direction at the centre of the triple-triad, suppressed similarly to the suppressed \mathfrak{T} s from the reorientation, but in the opposite (upper) super-triad to the suppressed reorientation \mathfrak{T} s (Figure. 1.8c); these synchronizing \mathfrak{T} s belong to the upper super-triad anyway. The upper super-triad would appear to ‘float’ on a negatively rotating centre while itself rotating with a $\dot{\theta}^-$ -spin in the opposite direction.

To conclude: No material difference results by rotating about other axes so this description gives all possibilities for the *given direction* of rotation. However, reorientation in the opposite direction is equally possible giving rise to the Stern-Gerlach phenomenon (2024a:§11A.6).

1.6 Triple-triad stability

As with the double triads the reorientating \mathfrak{S} s gain an additional rotation restricting their development when they materialize at the formation of the triple-triad. They become trions, and again, as with the double-triads, they jump away from the triple-triad.

The separation of the trions automatically lifts the non-intersection restriction on the three suppressed axial \mathfrak{S} s remaining at the origin, and they (the three suppressed \mathfrak{S} s) immediately generate the next cut for this space-Time system by repeating the above process; they each form three new \mathfrak{S} s, of which six reorient and travel along the imaginary axes. The process becomes a triple-triad pulsing in at the end of every cut (following materialization) followed by pulsing out during the next cut due to the action of the three \mathfrak{S} s remaining at the origin. Triple-triads are unable to spontaneously fly apart (disintegrate) because the origin of each triad would have to travel faster than the rate of space-Time production. Consequently their regeneration is permanent unless some catastrophic interaction intervenes.⁸ This repetitive action also maintains the formation of the synchronizing \mathfrak{S} s every cut.

1.7 Decay, formation of subsidiary particles

The triple-triad has a specific rotational form suggesting there could be other forms of rotation arising from the fundamental action. For example, suppose that after its generation, the triple-triad receives some form of stimulus (see §2) that causes its axes to reorient to another form of rotation much as a rotating ball hit by another object.

For example, if the triple-triad received a ‘blow’ its axes could be rotated, **or flipped**, in relation to its rotation axis as in Figure 1.9; so that its axial alignment has an axis in the plane of rotation – a slightly simpler rotational form in which its super-triads both *naturally* rotate in the same direction, when seen from above or below, that is along the axis of rotation without any need of the synchronizing rotation. Then there would be no need of the synchronizing rotation to keep its \mathfrak{S} s synchronized to maintain a constant distance apart.

Such an action is provided by a 135° flip (in human terms – the Universe does not need to know this value for the flip to occur) about the zz' axis in Figure 1.9.

Now the important part: if the *synchronizing rotation* was to remain in place it would no longer act to synchronize the two super triads but instead it would work against them so that they no longer met the

⁸ Jumping to Chapter 7 for example: two triple-triads being forced together due to the internal pressure inside a star.

constraints. However, the fundamental definition, has no built-in cause for their destruction so the non-intersection principle will cause them to move away as a group from the flipped particle. Humans would see this as an instantaneous ejection of a group of opposite-rotating \mathfrak{S} s.

Through the usual space-Time expansion, these rejected \mathfrak{S} s would instantaneously form a separate triple-triad as they would otherwise intersect each other's space-Time. But due to their former rotational action this new triple-triad would have to have its rotation in the opposite direction to the flipped triple-triad and, in *human ideas* twice the magnitude. But whereas the original triple-triad took on a synchronizing spin as it formed, the release of this additional spin was caused by the original triple-triad suddenly becoming synchronized, which means the synchronizing spin on release would automatically be synchronized itself. But, according to the fundamental principle, the \mathfrak{S} s rate of production of space-Time must be c^* , and this rate can only be achieved if the particle they form has, in human terms a radius half the size of the original triple-triad. That is, the tangential velocity must be c in the human relativistic expansion, which is attained in human geometric terms when the relativistic radius is half that of the original triple-triad. Human mathematics easily calculates that this radius is large enough to ensure this new form of particle could not disintegrate within a qut.

The qut is unaffected; the qul, however is fundamentally a human perception so $qul/2$ does not affect the concept of a minimal interval. The appearance of the synchronizing particle does not violate conservation as it was a balancing spin contained within $\dot{\theta}^+$.

Thus, the fundamental action automatically leads to three main types of particle, the original one, the flipped version, and the synchronizing spin now in the form of a particle. This is similar to the action in standard physics whereby a neutron can be caused to decay into a proton, electron and anti-neutrino. Consequently, the terms neutron for the original particle, proton for the flipped particle and electron for the synchronizing spin particle will be used, but it is necessary to show that the triple-triad forms have the same basic properties as found by human observation (see section 2.6).

Figure 1.9. In (a) the bottom group of axes $x'z'y'$, rotates anti-clockwise with a spin of $\dot{\theta}^+$. The upper group xyz , has the same spin but is upside down, so viewed from the top spins clockwise. The grey arrow at the top points in the direction of the synchronizing spin which, being upside

down, has the direction and value of $2\dot{\theta}^-$. The net effect is that the top half spins anti-clockwise. Diagram (b) shows (a) flipped about the zz' axis by 135° bringing the $x'x$ axis horizontal while maintaining the same $\dot{\theta}^+$ spin (which is the fundamental/foundational spin of the Universe) about K . The shaded areas represent the volumes (in the relativistic representation) of the original triads when the axes are fully developed. They are 'infinitesimally' thin due to the suppression of one \Im in each triad. The whole spins in the direction of the arrow at the bottom of diagram (b).

2.1 Force and motion

First I shall derive the concept of motion in RST, then the actions of trions and finally the concept of force and its transfer.

2.1 Linear motion983-580

Figure 2.1. A stable triple-triad at rest in the lattice of trace-points would have a basic rotation meeting the fundamental constraints. If the particle had a linear motion this, by addition of velocities, would affect the overall velocity of its \Im s at materialization. By the fundamental rule, their tangential velocity must be constant at c . For example if the point y' in diagram (C), the triple-triad of Figure 1.8b, moved across the page to the left, y' would have an additional velocity (to c) unless the triple-triad spontaneously changed either the direction of its rotation axis, or its rate of rotation, or the radial distances of the \Im s from O' , or a mixture of all three, so that all the \Im s travelled at c when they materialized. Similarly, for a \Im rotating in the opposite direction to the triple-triad's motion. That is, the triple-triad's motion is directly related to the motion of all six \Im s. Consequently, the particle's shape (in the relativistic representation) distorts due its velocity of propagation. In (b) a triple-triad travelling at $0.99c$ would have the shape shown.

Figure 2.2. The I, J, K space axes represent an initial direction of rotation of the triple-triad so that any change in the triple-triad orientation (ϕ, k) can be referred to I, J, K using three separate angles, α, β , and ζ to define angles between the i, j, k axes of the reorientated triple-triad and I, J, K where α represents a change of axis i relative to I in the IJ plane about axis K , β a change of j from J about I , and ζ a change of k from K about axis J . $\dot{\alpha}, \dot{\beta}, \dot{\zeta}$ are the corresponding rotations values in human perception. $\dot{\phi}$ is the combined rotation of $\dot{\alpha}$ and $\dot{\beta}$.

Note: the three angles of rotation derive directly from the definition of Time, which required the rotating action of \hat{T} to create the three-dimensional relativistic volume. This use of three angles again separates the foundational principle from standard theory; this time through Euler's principle which requires only two angles to describe a rotation.⁹ By removing the concept of three angles to cover three-dimensional rotation, Euler's method hides the 'how' of force which I argue is necessary to understand the principles governing motion and particle interactions at the fundamental level.

Thus the rule for motion is:

The velocity and total rotation of a particle have to meet the RST constraints for its space-Time generation. If this is not the case, either the velocity of its origin or the rate of rotation of the particle adjusts to compensate.

The next question on the describing force is how motion is instilled in a triple-triad. This requires extensive knowledge of the trion.

2.2 Trions cf, 2024a§5.3.1.

Section 1.6 showed that at the end of each cut the six axial particle \mathfrak{S} s materialize to become new points of Time. Their expansion disconnects them from the triple-triad in the same way the fundamental action creates an interval between trace-points. But, as in section 1.5, the reorientation of the \mathfrak{S} s during particle creation causes them to gain an extra rotation in two out of the three axial directions in which they develop so causing them to jump from point to point in a straight line as they materialize with the passing of every cut. They were thus given the temporary name **trion**. Taking the blue Y axis in Figure 2.3d as an example, it initially points in the red Y^* direction and then reorients into the initial position of the suppressed X^* \mathfrak{S} . This is a

⁹ See e.g Spiegel, M.R. 1987.

rotation, as given by the dash-dot line, around the Z^*OY axis. Consequently, when the \mathfrak{T} at the blue Y materializes, it can only regenerate as a trion in the Z^*OY direction; similarly for the \mathfrak{T} s at the other five generation points according to their individual orientations.

Figure 2.3. (a) Trion emission directions. These are upwards in relation to the formation process of the triple (and double) triads.

(c) Figure 2.3. 1.7a repeated. The axial colours in (d) relate to the original separate triads with their axis arrangements.

There are thus two trions travelling at c parallel to the X^*OZ direction, two parallel to the Z^*OY direction and two to the Y^*OX direction. Of these, the trions moving parallel to the OY direction carry a rotation in the sense of X rotating towards Z ; that is, an ξ -rotation as in Figure 2.3d. The heavy black circular arrow shows the rotation carried by this trion limiting its propagation to just the OY direction. The same form applies to all the other trions in the specific directions in which they are released. By their formation trions do not leave behind trace-points. Should two, or more collide they could not pass through each other, but they could, in the human sense of volume, rebound.

The next step demonstrates this is equivalent to what humans see as a force field.

2.3 Basic trion interaction

With only one direction of rotation for any given triple-triad and three axes of emission, as in Figure 2.3, the six trions are emitted in pairs having the same direction, one pair to each Cartesian dimension. Then:

1. The emitted trions are oriented according to the orientation of the emitting particle.
2. Each pair, by being emitted according to specific axial directions, carries a different rotation to the other pairs. For example, one pair might carry rotations $(\dot{\alpha}, \dot{\beta} [+]w, \dot{\xi} [+]w)$ or $(\dot{\alpha} [+]w, \dot{\beta}, \dot{\xi} [+]w)$ where $[+]$ means the rotation ‘contains’ both elements rather than the two being added together to make a single spin; e.g., the w part is the largest rotation possible so the $\dot{\beta}$ rotation cannot be added to it. If either member of the pair collided with another triple-triad (see §2.4) it could be absorbed. The recipient would then take on the $\dot{\alpha}$ rotation. But the $\dot{\beta} [+]w, \dot{\xi} [+]w$ parts *are* transmitted which means the recipient can orient to the $\dot{\beta} [+]w, \dot{\xi} [+]w$ parts; it just cannot register the actual spin-values $\dot{\beta}$ and $\dot{\xi}$ – it cannot spin faster than w .
3. The binding of two flows to the third, means that the trion's orientation is also determined in terms of its direction of travel.
4. Despite item 2, the set of all three rotations is, nevertheless, knowable. RST ties each of three dimensions to a rotation. The maximum rotation of each of these is w . Because w is a maximum value, the total spin of two or three dimensions is also w . (This is the RST-equivalent to Einstein’s relativistic addition of velocities:¹⁰ if the point has a rotation of w in three orthogonal directions its tangential velocity is still c).

Therefore, the trion emitted from a particular axis *always bears a directional relationship* with the orientation of the emitting particle. Furthermore, the orientation of the rotations relative to the super-triad axes depend on the particle species, their rotation direction being given as in Figure 1.8 with a change from the original particle (Figure 1.9a) to the flipped particle and the synchronizing spin particle (Figure 2.5 for both). The positive spin and synchronizing spin particle axes rotate such that one axis, arbitrarily designated xx' moves as though in an imaginary disc fixed ‘between’ the Y and Z axes. Thus the components of rotation in *any* frame of reference, not just the particle's own frame, can be related to the \mathfrak{S} s. Every action is therefore a spontaneous response to the fundamental rule.

¹⁰ Einstein ([1905] 1923: 51); cf §11.10 addendum on special relativity

Figure 2.4. Figure 1.9b reproduced to show the proton, or electron, triple-triad rotating in the plane of the dashed circle so that the XX' axis lies as if in a disc between the YY' and ZZ' axes which also rotate in the discs shown by the dotted lines.

The connection between a trion emitted from a particular axis and an emitting particle is shown in Figure 2.5 in terms of the three angles of rotation. Because the $\dot{\alpha}$, $\dot{\beta}$, and $\dot{\xi}$ rotations in diagrams (b) and (c) are distinct ('knowable') due to their values and directions they can be related to either a positive spin (diagram b) or a synchronizing spin (diagram c). A model of either can be made and whatever its orientation, its rotational form will never match the other. Diagram (a) relates the $\dot{\theta}$ rotation and $\dot{\xi}$ rotations (for a neutron); (b) and (c) represent trions, travelling in the direction of the main arrow, with an orientation given each by either a proton (for b) or electron (for c). (The same orientations are used for both for ease of comparison). The rotations will always be distinguishable from each other by a recipient of the trion as above and shown in Figure 2.5.

Figure 2.5. The rotation of a particle in terms of its axes.

Returning to the problem of force, or energy transfer, envisage a trion colliding with a triple-triad. Its point-like structure would be able to pass in between the particle's space-Time triads as in Figure 1.9 without intersecting them. But it would not pass completely through them within one qut because within this time the triple-triad would contract. This happens equally in both the natural representation and the relativistic representation described here. The trion's \mathfrak{S} s will then become positioned at the recipient's origin where they will be stuck because the recipient's own \mathfrak{S} s must still expand. The trion cannot, in this instant, pass through them without intersecting them. Consequently, the trion will be held in the triple-triad centre. Its spin will be absorbed as the recipient changes motion, so the trion cannot be passed on later. The particle's

\mathfrak{S} s will operate from this spinning centre. The rotations carried by the trion and the triple-triad will each be orientated according to their individual \mathfrak{S} s. These orientations may not initially match, but will need to do so if the constraints for space-Time development are to be met; that is, the $\dot{\alpha}$, $\dot{\beta}$, and $\dot{\xi}$ components of rotation of both particles (the recipient and trion) must line up – as follows:

As derived in section 2.1, the rotation of a triple-triad is determined by its separate \mathfrak{S} s. Each \mathfrak{S} , in the relativistic representation, has a different three-dimensional track relative to the other \mathfrak{S} s depending on $\dot{\alpha}$, $\dot{\beta}$, and $\dot{\xi}$:¹¹ As the trion is emitted from a given triple-triad, the same will have to be true for its fundamental rotations. These rotations are specified, firstly, by the trion's \mathfrak{S} s even though they travel as a point-like bundle. Secondly, the neutron's flip to form the proton and electron places the $\dot{\xi}$ rotation in a plane at 45° to the Y and Z axes. These actions, relevant to both triple-triad and absorbed trion, keys them into aligning their axes.

Finally, RST dictates that because the trion contains two rotations with magnitude w , it cannot change its orientation because it cannot rotate faster than w (nor slower). This means that the triple-triad's \mathfrak{S} s will have to change orientation to fit the trion's axial directions, *turning the other way up if necessary*. This inversion will not involve any additional spin because the triple-triad is rotating anyway so the individual axes can key in during the qut; nor is the RST-generator involved so the fundamental rule the generator governs is not violated. Thus, the α , β and ξ angles of both particles will also match due to the distinct nature of their rotations.

The action of emission, transmission and absorption of a trion details how instructions are carried from one particle to another. Next: the effect on the motion of the recipient.

2.4 Change in motion

From section 2.1, the velocity and total rotation of a particle have to be consistent with the constraints for its space-Time generation. That is, a change in velocity implies a change in rotation, and vice versa where the velocity refers to the relativistic representation – a change in particle rotation creates a change in particle velocity or vice versa. In the natural representation space-Time has emerged as a set of distinct trace-points in the lattice so that 'velocity' would relate to the number of qut's to change position from one trace point to another, equating in human interpretation to the number of quts it takes to travel one qul (in curved space). or in Euclidean space the number of quts it takes to travel one qul^r (2023a:§4.5).

Referring to Figures 2.2 and 2.5, a proton has a $\dot{\theta}$ rotation plane which itself can rotate with $\dot{\xi}$ -rotation, so that $\dot{\xi}$ is the rotation that will determine the velocity required by the particle to maintain the tangential

¹¹ This is determinable mathematically but nevertheless is a result of the foundational principle irrespective of any mathematical consequences. The $\dot{\xi}$ rotation, for example, varies between 10^{-17} and one radian per qut. A trion rotates at one radian, approximately 57.3°, per qut.

rotation of its \mathfrak{T} s at c . Consequently, the motion of a triple-triad, such as a proton or electron, is governed by its $\dot{\xi}$ -rotation only, though the $\dot{\alpha}$ and $\dot{\beta}$ rotations determine how the trion's $\dot{\xi}$ -rotation fits into the triple-triad rotation. That is, the system ensures that a change in the $\dot{\xi}$ -rotation is passed on if the absorbing triple-triad has a different value of that rotation to that of the trion.

Significantly, section 2.2 (Figure 2.3) derived that only two of the six trions emitted by a triple-triad would carry the $\dot{\xi}$ -rotation. Of the others, two would carry $(\dot{\alpha}, \dot{\beta} [+]w, \dot{\xi} [+]w)$ or $(\dot{\alpha} [+]w, \dot{\beta}, \dot{\xi} [+]w)$. As $\dot{\alpha}$ and $\dot{\beta}$, have different rates of rotation from $\dot{\xi}$ they would provide different actions to those provided by $\dot{\xi}$; see (2024:§7.7).

2.5 The concept of Force - particle interactions and 'mass'.

The concept of force is intuitive to humans and, by this intuition, is causal, a problem that worried Newton (1693) with respect to his gravitational theory – action at a distance with no recognizable cause. Electricity is fundamental to human life. Yet no-one has determined what it actually is. Current is conveyed by electrons but, see¹² standard physics argues over whether these (electrons) are corpuscles, waves or fields. Protons have charge supposedly opposite to electrons but why do like charges repel and unlike charges attract? What is the difference between the two – if there is any? And how can particles tell whether to come together or move apart?

Section 2.4 based on the single foundational principle has suggested some generalization of the nature of force as follows: imagine a particle A moving in some arbitrary direction with speed v_a and rotation $(\dot{\theta}_a, \dot{\xi}_a)$ where the subscript refers to the particle. The rotations carried by the six trions A emits are specified by A 's rotation. Suppose a trion carrying $\dot{\xi}_a$ rotation is absorbed by a second particle, B , of the same species, for example two neutrons, whose rotations before absorption are $(\dot{\theta}_i, \dot{\xi}_i)$ where subscript i refers to the initial speed of particle B . Without the absorption, the continued existence of B during the next cut (and all subsequent cuts) would be due to the expansion of the three \mathfrak{T} s that remained at its centre, O'_i . These \mathfrak{T} s moved with O'_i during the previous cut. Consequently when these \mathfrak{T} s are released to generate nine new \mathfrak{T} s (of which three will remain at the triple-triad's origin) the six \mathfrak{T} s that materialize at the end of the new cut will all have motions commensurate with B 's velocity of \mathbf{v}_i (in terms of a set of I, J, K axes fixed at some given time (real numbers), such as the beginning of the previous cut). Without other factors, this velocity will determine the rotations at the outset of the new cut.

Now imagine the absorption occurs. Then, as $(\dot{\theta}_i, \dot{\xi}_i)$ results from B 's velocity, \mathbf{v}_i before absorption, B 's new generation of \mathfrak{T} s will be free to take on the rotations, $(\dot{\theta}_a, \dot{\xi}_a)$ that the absorbed trion carries. As

¹² Leggett and Garg (1985); Hobson (2005, 2013); Mahdi (2014:1); Barak (2016:2); Joshi (2016:1132); Jones (2002:230); Gao (2016:15); Dorato (2014); Sebens (2019a:30); (McDonald 2018); (Hubert 2018)

$\dot{\theta}_a$ is the combination of the rotations $\dot{\alpha} [+]w$, $\dot{\beta} [+]w$, it operates in orienting axes only, only $\dot{\xi}_a$ has any transferable magnitude and this will be the rotation taken on by the six \mathfrak{T} s that will generate the space-Time for B in its ‘pulsing out’ phase. The \mathfrak{T} s automatically carry the orientation angles (β, ξ) and the remaining parameters $(\alpha, \dot{\alpha}, \dot{\beta})$ must adjust to meet the constraints. Therefore the recipient’s origin O'_i starts the qut at its old velocity \mathbf{v}_i , but the new $\dot{\xi}$ amends this velocity to \mathbf{v}_a with respect to the external I, J, K axes. Note there is a difference here from the intuitive addition of velocities in mathematical physics. For example, if $\dot{\xi}_a$ is greater than $\dot{\xi}_i$ then the change of rotation is from $\dot{\xi}_i$ to $\dot{\xi}_a$ and thus the change in velocity is from \mathbf{v}_i to \mathbf{v}_a , and not a straight addition $\mathbf{v}_i + \mathbf{v}_a$.¹³

If the particles are of different species then the positive and negative spins cause the direction of propagation to be different. Absorption of a trion carrying the same spins as the recipient would cause no change in rotation or speed, but the recipient’s direction and thus velocity would change (2024a:§6.4.1).

If a particle carrying high $\dot{\xi}_i$ enters an area where its motion will be restricted through the absorption of trions from particles in the area carrying a different spin $\dot{\xi}_j$ less than $\dot{\xi}_i$, the particle will, at the instant of absorption, have an excess rotation. Reversing the first process described above, it will instantaneously emit the excess rotation in the form of a trion carrying off the change in spins which can be denoted as $(\Delta \dot{\alpha}, \Delta \dot{\beta}, \Delta \dot{\xi})$. That is, this form of trion, temporarily called **Δ -trion**, will be a pure rotation particle.¹⁴ If the motion is not restricted then it will continue propagating in accordance with rotation $\dot{\xi}_i$. Again this implies that the actual measurement values we use only arise as a result of our wish to measure and calculate.

RST implies this emission-absorption process can work both ways between particles but *not necessarily in tandem*. All triple-triads emit $\dot{\xi}$ -trions in a continual stream. Thus exchange between two freely moving particles is completely random. However, proton-electron orbits can be set up, as a series of interactions between them can orientate their motions and thus rotations and trion emissions to coordinate. This process is very much a hit and miss affair; but conducted at nearly 10^{24} trions issued per second it would appear as if each triple-triad had a ‘force field’ about it.¹⁵

The force inverse square rule applies: if an imaginary sphere is placed around a trion emitter, its surface can be divided into σ -sized sub-areas. Then if the sphere’s radius increases, the probability of each σ -sized sub-area receiving a trion reduces as the square of the distance. Furthermore, a trion has a straight-line

¹³ This situation refers to the rotational aspect. $\mathbf{v}_i + \mathbf{v}_a$ would produce a duplication of the spin in \mathbf{v}_i and thus violate the law of conservation of energy. The usual addition of velocities in physics remains unchanged.

¹⁴ If a Δ -trion were to be absorbed by, for example, an electron, it would have to align in such a way that the electron’s final rotations would meet the constraints otherwise no interaction could take place. So, on receipt of a Δ -trion, both trion and recipient together, align (whereas in the receipt of a force photon the recipient only aligns). Then the absorbing particle shows a change in speed but not necessarily a change in direction. The change in direction depends upon the relative rotations of the two particles and their directions of travel. This form of emission is particularly important for visual reception of light.

¹⁵ See measurement test (2024:ch11).

velocity of c . This fits human perception that force travels with the speed of light,¹⁶ especially in the case of the Δ -trion. Thus trions fit the role of the photon and will be referred to as ξ -photons for transfer of electromagnetic effects, and Δ -photons for light and gamma-rays et cetera.

As above, RST force radiates out from a triple-triad much as a light beam from a lighthouse that rotates through three dimensions. The force around a particle is therefore

not a continuum, as in physical theory, but disjointed.

Furthermore, *there is no recoil, nor equal and opposite reaction* in the emission or reception process of triple-triad type particles and photons, contrary to the assumption of physical theory.¹⁷ RST photons do not carry ‘momentum’ in the standard theory sense.¹⁸ Finally, the explicit form of this field suggests that it is the only possible form of ‘force’ transfer (including gravity [2024:§7.7]). The remaining question is whether the three triple-triad types react identically to ‘force’. If not why not?

2.6 Do all particles react identically?

The original triple-triad (neutron) requires a synchronizing spin to exist. The proton has stable rotation at the same rate as the neutron without the necessity of a synchronizing spin but with a different axial orientation of its triads to its spin. The electron is the ejected synchronizing spin having twice the rate of rotation of the proton but half its radius. The individual velocities of these particles is governed by the angle of their triads to their spin so giving them different minimum velocities through the lattice. Then, by introducing measurement, SRT can be converted to equations of motion (2024:§ch11). These give to approximately 99.99% accuracy the human experimental inertia (inertial mass) of each particle relative to each other.

2.6.1 Particle attraction and repulsion

Inertial differences are not the only differences. The electron and proton rotate in opposite directions given by the $\dot{\theta} = (\dot{\alpha} + \dot{\beta})$ -rotation. In Figure 1.9, rotation from the neutron to proton orientation arises around the z - z' axes which brings the x -axis into a plane orthogonal to the K axis. As the x -axis rotates through the α -angle it would then be the $\dot{\alpha}$ component of rotation that is responsible for the electron rotation.

Then if an ξ -photon released by a proton carrying $\dot{\alpha}$ -rotation is absorbed by an electron with $-\dot{\alpha}$ -rotation, the $\dot{\alpha}$ rotations of the photon and electron have to coordinate (section 2.3). The receiving electron may then have to turn the other way up. As the rotations of all particles are defined via the first point of Time, if the electron and proton have the same orientation then their opposing rotations will cause them to move in opposite directions. Thus, if the electron has to turn the other way up on absorbing a photon emitted by a proton it must have *originally been moving away* from the proton and its change in orientation will

¹⁶ cf Einstein [1905]1923:52; Kraus 1(984:383)

¹⁷ Bueche (1975:48); Hawking and Mlodinov (2011:134)

¹⁸ Kuhlmann (2018:§5.1.1.2)

cause it to move towards the proton. The opposite effect would be true for particles with the same $\dot{\alpha}$ -rotation. Figure 6.9 shows the effect.

Figure 6.9. Attraction-repulsion effect. If a particle with velocity \mathbf{u} (approach) is hit by an $\dot{\xi}$ -photon carrying $\dot{\xi}$ -rotation it would move along \mathbf{u}_1 if the signs of the $\dot{\alpha}$ -rotation of the $\dot{\xi}$ -photon and absorber are different, or \mathbf{u}_2 if the same.

Thus the so-called electric charge of human physical theory is nothing more than a reaction to the differing rotations of the electron and proton in RST.

Note a surprising effect of this action. If, say, an electron is travelling directly towards a proton its change of direction will still take place, but in a direction *away* from the proton. Further interactions will then turn it back *towards* the proton.¹⁹ The same turning away from a direct approach applies to all particles so that freely moving triple-triads *can never come into contact* except under intense pressures, as, for example, in stars.

Varying values of $\dot{\xi}$ rotation would not cause 'electric charge' to be variable. Particles already 'attracted' or coordinated with each other exchange $\dot{\xi}$ -photons carrying $\dot{\xi}$ commensurate with their joint velocity and so merely maintain position relative to each other. The 'electric' attraction is caused by the $\dot{\alpha}$ rotation carried by the ($\dot{\alpha}$ [+] w) component of an $\dot{\xi}$ -photon implying *speed* does not change relative to the source of the $\dot{\alpha}$ -component. Nevertheless, in the frame of an external observer there would be an observed change in direction of the electron and thus an observed change in *velocity*. Einstein (1905b) covers magnetism.

The effect on the neutron depends through which half of the triad system the $\dot{\xi}$ -photon arrives. If the signs of the photon's $\dot{\alpha}$ -component and neutron $\dot{\theta}$ -rotations cause it to move away from the emitter, the probability is that, because the neutron is rotating, the next $\dot{\xi}$ -photon will arrive through the other half,

¹⁹ The change of direction can be calculated once the Time mechanism has been tested against measurement as in section 11A.9

bearing the opposite $\dot{\theta}$ sign causing the neutron to move diagonally towards the emitter – it oscillates. Similarly, particles near the neutron will oscillate in accordance with neutron emissions.

2.6.2 Electron Orbits and force in the RST picture

As above, photon exchanges between proton and electron can coordinate their orientations so that every time an electron receives an $\dot{\xi}$ -photon from the proton it changes direction diagonally towards the proton. Between photon receipts it would propagate in a straight line so that its orbital radius depends on its speed and distance from the proton. At approximately 10^{24} photons emitted and 10^7 orbits per second the process is stable.

Should the electron receive a photon from an external source that increases its speed the possibilities are: (1) The increase in its speed takes it so far from the proton that further photons from the proton only marginally affect the electron's progress – it escapes completely. (2) The increase in its speed causes it to travel further out but not fast enough to avoid it receiving regular photons – it will move further between successive interactions with the proton, with a larger orbit. (1) and (2) will give the appearance of the 'force of attraction' to the proton falling off with distance. (3) It only gains a small *temporary* increase in speed before being held in its initial orbit. If in (2) it returns to its original orbit, it releases a Δ -photon reducing its energy. The RST system contradicts standard ideas (cf2024§64.3) but the equations of motion (2024:§11a.9-9.3) demonstrate that, correctly applied, RST agrees almost exactly with observed orbital radii and emissions.

It is now possible to understand nuclear construction.

3.1 Nuclei according to RST

As above the formation of atomic nuclei needs strong pressure, as found in stars, to overcome the natural tendency of nucleons to remain apart. Parallel to current theory the number of gravitons pulling nucleons together (internal stellar pressure) increases the nucleon velocities towards each other sufficiently to overcome the repulsive $\dot{\xi}$ -photon flow in the opposite direction.

Additionally, unlike the expected repulsion of nuclear protons in standard theory, the fundamental formation of the $\dot{\xi}$ -photon field (sections 2.3-4) allows protons and neutrons to rest in contact with each other without 'electrically' interacting. It should then be possible to arrange their orientation so that their $\dot{\xi}$ -photons do not intercept one-another in their grouping. Consequently, models or graphics can be easily set up to determine possible structures.

The result suggests that, apart from hydrogen, the helium nucleus, being the most symmetrical and simplest composite formation, is the most stable and forms a basis for more complex nuclei – as expected by standard theory. Considering the enormous pressure of formation, the triple-triads must arrange themselves into the smallest possible volume without intersecting each other at any stage of their rotation.

The models/graphics then determine that the neutrons form a central single ring structure up to fluorine, and double (closed ‘figure of 8’) rings up to chlorine. This allows gravity to hold the neutrons in place with the protons bound to them also gravitationally,²⁰ while the ξ -photons pass without obstruction from the nucleus in accordance with the directed emission processes described in section 2.3. It is suited to this arrangement as it causes the immediate receipt, each cut, of gravitons between the neutrons. Similarly, the protons can be orientated to exchange gravitons with the neutrons each cut. Then as the nucleus itself rotates, an *apparently* continuous ξ -photon field would be created about it where electrons may be captured.

The structure of the group-two atoms plus phosphorous from group three follows. To detail every atom would be beyond the aim of this work, so this section is only superficially explained with just carbon being given a diagrammatical treatment to give the general idea of neutron-proton arrangements. Section 3.2 will then investigate major considerations that arise from building these nuclei throwing new light on the role of neutrinos.

Because hydrogen (^1H) is a single proton nucleus its method of bonding to an electron will be different to all other elements. The Time concept shows that in atoms such as lithium, the proton has to adopt a specific orientation so that its ξ -photon emissions do not interfere with the other nucleons. This means that the outer electron would not orbit centrally around the nucleus but would always orbit to one side. In the hydrogen atom the processes briefly outlining electron orbits in section 2.8 would cause the electron to pass around the nucleus. This special hydrogen orbit has further implications. For example, if two oxygen atoms bond, the shared electrons would orbit in a plane that lies between them. But for hydrogen, if another atom gains a share of its electron, the motion of the hydrogen nucleus would change so that the electron still passes around it. Only hydrogen could react in this way because its nucleus consists of a single proton.²¹ As a result it would easily form and release bonds, and in particular, whereas other atoms would only be able to bond on the side in which their electrons orbit, hydrogen can bond in any direction. In general, a chemical bond is formed simply by an electron oscillating between two atoms. The form of the oscillation would depend on the structure of the relevant nuclei which may be either electron donors or recipients.

After hydrogen, the Time scheme places helium as the most symmetrical, and efficient, arrangement of any nucleus. Its two neutrons conjoin diagonally with the protons filling opposite corners, see Figure 3.1b. This structure would be gravitationally extremely ‘strong’ as all the neutrons are in complete contact with each other. As a result, in nuclear synthesis new elements would be forged as near as possible around this basic design. Its symmetrical arrangement will cause, all four nucleons to have similar radii of rotation as the nucleus itself rotates. This gives helium the lowest possible average nucleon rotation (lowest average value for the ξ rotation), that is, lowest energy of all the elements apart from hydrogen. The result would

²⁰ The action of gravity described in Thompson (2024:§7.7) is identical to the above force field except it operates from the β rotation with a strength 1.24×10^{-35} of the ξ -photon and is thus orthogonal to the ξ -rotation (force).

²¹ Excluding its isotopes.

be that the electrons could pass around the nucleus without losing contact making an exceptionally strong connection.

In the lithium nucleus, the helium base remains intact and its associated electrons would still be strongly connected. Models show that two additional neutrons would be required forming a ring (see Figure 3.1) against which two of the protons bind to the neutrons as close to inside the ring in helium formation as possible. The third proton has to bind externally. The third proton's greater rotation radius, as the nucleus rotates, means that it travels faster than the inner protons and thus its ξ -photon emissions would carry a higher ξ -spin. Its associated electron therefore travels faster with a larger orbital radius (section 2.8) and is always to the proton's side of the nucleus allowing it to be more easily torn away.

Beryllium would require another variation. Its atom has four protons suggesting that it should be the combination of two helium groups giving it four neutrons as well. However, this does not form a stable arrangement as two of the protons would be conjoining (thus interacting); while the helium nuclei can be brought together in a star, as soon as the pressure is removed they will tend to disintegrate unless the extra neutron is included. The result is that the five neutrons of beryllium form a pentagon with two protons inside the ring and two outside. This is more symmetrical than lithium with the two outer protons being attached more closely to the centre of nuclear revolution than the single external proton in lithium. Consequently, the radius of the outer two (valence) electrons will be less than that of the lithium atom and will be more tightly held. Additionally, the two valence electrons, being symmetrically arranged can be held by either proton. As a result, the theoretical size of the lithium atom should be larger than that of the beryllium atom and the latter should be less reactive – as observed in experiment.

Oxygen is an interesting example of an atom that mainly gains electrons. It shows that according to RST this trait in any electron acceptor is due to the nuclear structure rather than the standard shell theory, which is only incidental. Oxygen is also one of the most densely packed nuclei. As the number of *outer* protons increases (see shielding effect later), the number of positive spinning ξ -photons passing out of the nucleus increases compared to just the one outer stream (i.e. ignoring the inner protons), say, in the lithium atom. Only very few of these photons will be absorbed by the orbiting electrons leaving a large number free to be absorbed by other nearby electrons; so if a donor atom is nearby its electron may be 'attracted'. The oxygen model is a direct combination of four helium nuclei producing an octagonal neutron ring with four protons inside it and four outside. This can be achieved with minimum volume only if the outer proton pairs have an angle of 104.5° between them. Then the simplest bonds (with hydrogen to give water) will be set at this angle as found in experiment.²² The RST structure of carbon and nitrogen nuclei also corroborate with bond angles observed in experiment.

²² (Engel and Reid 2006:555)

Oxygen is an oddity as, of all the atoms, this one possible arrangement places its outer protons in the plane of rotation of the nucleus. This means they have to be positioned in pairs on alternating sides of the neutron ring. Their associated electrons will thus orbit in pairs with only a very small separation of just six quils between the electrons in each pair. This separation is too narrow to allow more than one helix path of an orbiting hydrogen nucleus. As a result, although there are four external electrons, only one electron from each pair can bond with a hydrogen atom. This can be either of the two electrons per pair so that the bonds between oxygen and other atoms are much stronger than would otherwise be the case. Of the four protons inside the ring there are two that stick out slightly above and below. These create two separate electron orbits corresponding to standard theory's lone pair. (Voet and Voet (2004:39-43) give a detailed description of oxygen-hydrogen bonding which fits the RST atomic structure).

Nitrogen and phosphorus: Models show that nitrogen being the next element after carbon, has a similar structure. The main difference is that the neutron ring contains an extra member making it a heptagon. This gives room for the additional proton to reside *inside* it. A similar case applies in phosphorus except that two heptagons form a double ring joined by two extra neutrons. Both these cases create the tetragonal arrangement of the valence electrons also found in carbon (as in Figure 3.1). The arrangement suggests that the extra internal proton could create many of the biochemical properties special to these elements. This RST concept would be more pronounced in phosphorus than nitrogen. In the latter it fails to create a fifth bond because the associated electron would travel well within the orbits of the outer electrons and is shielded by them. Nevertheless, this inside proton, and associated electron, may activate amino acids to form proteins. The important radical is ammonia and in essence this is attached to a carbon chain when an amino acid is formed. This arrangement suggests that when two amino groups join to form a peptide the reactive parts use nitrogen's inner electron to create a nitrogen-carbon bond. The outer electron it replaces becomes redundant because these two electrons essentially have the same orientation in relation to the nucleus, so they cannot both connect to atoms at the same time without a collision. On the other hand the outer electron becomes a 'prison gate' so that the carbon-nitrogen is a short strong bond as seen in experiment.

Carbon consists of six protons and six neutrons. These numbers are exactly equivalent to three helium groups and, perhaps unsurprisingly, this is how the models based on the Time concept arrange the carbon nucleus. This makes it one of the most symmetric elements. Nevertheless, this symmetry provides a wonderful variety of possible bonds with other atoms. The structure given by the Time mechanism is unique because it is the only one to contain six neutrons arranged in a hexagonal ring, and its six protons arranged symmetrically, so that three fall evenly spaced outside the ring and two inside as shown in Figure 3.1a,b. The two internal protons are much closer to the axis of rotation of the nucleus; thus their electrons have a much smaller orbital radius than the others and are both shielded from bonding as well as being more tightly held to their protons. The sixth proton is attached between two of the three symmetrically placed outer protons but, whereas they radiate their photons upwards in the figure, the sixth proton radiates downwards thus placing its electron in an orbit at the point of the tetrahedron.

Figure 3.1. The Time structure of the Carbon nucleus as determined by modelling and graphics. The nucleus consists of six neutrons, pale grey, and six protons, dark grey. The neutrons form a hexagon as in diagram (a). The arrangement of the helium building blocks is clearly visible in diagram (b) as each consists of two protons and two neutrons. Two protons lie fully inside the hexagonal ring of neutrons and a third is partly inside. The other three stick out around the outside. The nucleus is held together by gravity and rotates as a unit about the centre of the hexagon, which means that the outer protons have to travel further and faster than those inside the hexagon. Unlike in standard theory, the corresponding electrons then also rotate *faster* than those associated with the inner protons. Their orbits are shown by the rings in diagram (c) (not to scale). The thin ring represents the orbits of the electrons belonging to the two innermost protons; these will be shielded by the outer electrons. The other rings at the top of the tetrahedron represent the orbits of electrons belonging to the outside protons. The fourth heavy ring at the point of the tetrahedron belongs to the electron of the remaining proton. Only the four outer electrons can form bonds, the positions of which are determined by the protons forming the corners of a tetrahedron.

Organic bond structures and equivalent chemistry fill an entire discipline so will not be considered here. But a look at the projected electron orbits in Figure 3.1 suggests they may fit closely the angles and radii found in experiment. Instead, a much more important subject is raised in conjunction with these composite atoms which solves one of the greatest mysteries of current physics (and astrophysics).

First, the Time scheme deduces that the orbits of the electrons always have to be in the same direction as the rotation of the protons. Second, the protons all have to rotate in the same direction in the nucleus so that they don't interfere electrically with each other. In any case they are all bound to the neutron rings. This at first sight may seem to indicate that no photons can be emitted downwards to form the peak of the tetrahedron. However, recall how the basic particle, the neutron is created. The Σ s that form it had to reorient and, this can take place in one of two directions giving the Stern-Gerlach effect (2024:§11A.6). Then for half the particles created, the photons can and must be emitted in the **up** direction, as in the Figures, while for the other half they can and must be emitted in the opposite **down** direction.

The impact is seen in the projected formation of nuclei. The process, according to standard theory, starts when the internal pressure of a star, such as the sun, causes a proton and electron to form a neutron.²³ This neutron subsequently binds with other protons to form, first, a deuteron and then a 'light' helium nucleus. The latter has just one neutron which means that only one of the protons can have a gravitational binding to it resulting in an unstable combination. Consequently two of these light helium nuclei have to combine to give the usual two neutron–two proton formation (leaving two protons over). This process is given two twists in the Time scheme – both completely unexpected in standard theory: the first is that the protons can only adhere (gravitationally) to the neutrons provided one of the two is an 'up' nucleon and the other 'down' (in the Stern-Gerlach sense as in the previous paragraph). In the case of more complex atoms similar states arise so that, for example, carbon has three up protons and three down and similarly for the neutrons. Solving the second twist requires new information not yet uncovered.

3.2 The role of neutrinos

To see the second twist it is necessary to look at the equations of motion (Thompson 2024§11). Solving these by trial and error was useful as it became apparent that a change in the $\dot{\beta}$ -rotation (equivalent to a change in the β -orientation) gave significant differences in the corresponding velocities. These angles are fixed for the neutron, proton and electron but it was apparent that if the β -angle of the electron were to be increased by 90 or 180° giving a higher $\dot{\beta}$ -rotation, particles with reduced velocities might be created. The first gives a particle with linear velocity reduced by 207.74 times and the second a reduction of 3486.109 times. These are so close to the accepted 'masses' of the muon and tau particles that the concept can be assumed to account for their existence. They, according to the Time structure, have a helix path with cycles of approximately 10.5 and 8 qut respectively reflecting the greater 'energy' 'stored' in the $\dot{\beta}$ component.²⁴ The process suggests that if a photon or 'other particle' carrying sufficient rotation/energy (for example an energetic cosmic ray in the high atmosphere) is absorbed by an electron, it would cause deformation of the electron in the form shown in Figure 2.1 to such an extent that the particle could not meet any constraints.

²³ Goldberg and Scadron (1995:177-187)

²⁴ Nucleons and electrons propagate with a cycle of 18.97 qut.

But if the particle orientation changes, the high rotation (energy) is ‘siphoned off’ to maintain the orientation with a corresponding reduction in velocity.

The reverse is attained if the muon or tau absorbs less ‘energetic’ (lower rotation) photons and emits the excess angle in the form of a rotational particle. Similar types of particles can be found for the proton.²⁵ Standard physics has noted the emission of neutrinos in the electron-muon and tau processes which are filled by the neutrino in the above RST processes (cf Hughes 1985: 94-98).²⁶ Considering that the increase in electron orientation (relative to its spin) to produce a muon, or discharge from a muon as it returns to an electron, has to be carried by some sort of particle, it would seem the standard theory’s neutrino would be the RST carrier. That is, the neutrino carries 90 or 180° rotations in the β -orientation direction (i.e., higher $\dot{\beta}$). The same process occurs in the interaction when a neutron is converted to a proton plus electron and antineutrino, or vice versa²⁷ – a particle must be released to take away the excess spin (energy), or vice versa, with an antineutrino.

As an example of nucleus formation according to the Time scheme, should the nuclear protons in Figure 3.1 all rotate in the same direction, their $\dot{\xi}$ -photons would only be emitted in one direction relative to the nucleus. Then all the electrons would be held on one side of the nucleus only. However, the formation of complex nuclei in stars would, according to the Time scheme, require specific gravitational binding directions of the nucleons: half must transmit photons ‘upwards’ and half ‘downwards’ in relation to their rotation. The necessary variation is provided by the Stern-Gerlach mechanism, which also applies to both the $\dot{\xi}$ -photon and graviton fields. However, the correct number of ‘up’ and ‘down’ nucleons may not be present in a specific nuclear fusion cell, that is, a small volume created by stellar pressure where nuclei are created. Imbalances can be overcome if the relevant nucleons undergo a Stern-Gerlach change in orientation. This would be provided by neutrinos/antineutrinos operating on nucleon orientation angles by the 90 or 180° change as required. This is not dependent on immediate availability, as any imbalance can be corrected by the absorption or emission of one or more neutrinos *or* antineutrinos to give the required numbers of up and down nucleons. The required change in angle is 180° from ‘up’ to ‘down’ whereas different neutrinos give different angle changes so that the formation of helium, or more complex nuclei, may end up absorbing electron-neutrinos and giving off muon or tau neutrinos carrying rotational effects of 90 or 180° respectively in the RST model.

Specifically, therefore, when three heliums are forced together to create a carbon nucleus there must be three protons emitting photons in one direction and three in the reverse. This would be required to give the protons the correct binding directions so that their gravitons pass into the neutrons. The nucleus will split apart otherwise – thus producing a randomness in construction. In Figure 3.1 the lower inner proton

²⁵ E.g. Higgs boson 3/2 generation proton. 2nd generation proton (cosmic ray) with energy 10²¹eV (2024:§10.3.3)

²⁶ (cf Hughes 1985: 94-98)

²⁷ In physical language $n^0 \leftrightarrow p + e \pm \nu$ during the change of neutron (n^0) to proton (p), e electron ν neutrino)

obviously emits downwards. The other inner proton also does so, as there is plenty of room for its photons to bypass the other nucleons – all the nucleons rotate as a whole so that the emission directions in relation to each other are fixed for the existence of the atom. The fourth external proton originally belonged to the helium nucleus opposite so that it emits downwards while the other three external protons emit upwards. This means that as a result of the protons binding to the neutrons, their ξ -photons are dispatched in directions that will fit the orbits given in Figure 3.1. The same principle applies to all atomic nuclei.²⁸

3.3 Chemical reactions

This brief section mentions two important off-shoots of RST, which fit in with chemical investigations.

First, RST implies the electric field about a proton consists of a pair of ξ -photons radiating out every cut in a single beam creating a discontinuous field. The proton rotates about 10^{16} times and emits about 10^{23} ξ -photon pairs every second.²⁹ This mechanism creates specific bonding points and allows them to be broken. A broken bond is not reconstituted immediately because time is needed for a proton to pass a new photon to the electron. This can take several thousand cut, sufficient time for molecules in a reaction to reorganize. The strength and apparent type of bonding, and the possibility of protons attracting electrons from outside the atom is explained by the nuclear structure rather than by group quantum rules. While the structure builds up from element to element in an ordered way to give a general group system very close to that of standard chemistry, each structure has differences that explain variations from the group.

Atomic neutrality is statistically attained when the number of ξ -photons emitted by a nucleus is balanced by the number of ξ -photons emitted by the electrons. Because of the single emission direction of photons, the emission from orbiting electrons is polarized relative to their motion so that electrons from the same atom do not interfere with each other. Moreover, this directional emission also applies to protons, allowing the proton and electron to keep in touch.

3.4 Conclusion

Rotation-space-Time answers many unsolved problems of current cosmology, particularly explaining the action of force at a distance, the structure of nuclei and neutrinos, and has the benefit it can be Popper-tested. Knowledge of the action of force, which mathematics by itself cannot provide, demonstrates ‘hidden from observation’ effects and moreover suggests that mathematical physics is on the ‘wrong’ path, especially over the different ideas, (bag models, drip models, quarks etc) for nuclei construction. RST

²⁸ Neutrino propagation needs further work which is not included here.

²⁹ The rotation depends on the u velocity which on Earth moving through the expanding cosmos is probably in the relativistically affected measurement range. At $c \xi$ will be approximately 10^{17} qulqut⁻¹

provides a new method of enquiry, in particular, over periodic table group properties and chemistry based on nuclear structure.

Bibliography

- Bachall, J.N. 2004. *Solving the mystery of the missing neutrinos*, NobelPrize.org. Nobel Media AB 2019. Retrieved 23rd May 2019 from the World Wide Web: <https://www.nobelprize.org/prizes/themes/solving-the-mystery-of-the-missing-neutrinos>
- Barak, S. (2016) On the Essence of Electric Charge Part 1. HAL open science: <https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/hal-01401332>
- Bueche (1975) Bueche, F. 1977. *Principles of Physics*. New York: McGraw-Hill Book Co.
- Dorato, M. and Laudisa, F. 2014. *Realism and instrumentalism about the wave function. How should we choose?* arXiv:1401.4861v1. Retrieved 19th March 2018.
- Einstein [1905b] 1923 “On the electrodynamics of moving bodies”, in: W. Perrett and G.B. Jeffery (trans.). *The Principle of Relativity – A collection of original memoirs of the special and general theory of relativity – H.A. Lorentz, A. Einstein, H. Minkowski and H. Weyl*. New York: Dover Publications.
- Engel, T. and Reid, P.J. 2006. *Physical Chemistry*. San Francisco: Pearson Education, Inc.
- Gao, S. 2016. *Meaning of the Wave Function; In search of the ontology of quantum mechanics*. arXiv: 1610:027381. Retrieved 30th September 2018.
- Goldberg, H.S. and Scadron, M.D. 1995. *Physics of Stellar Evolution and Cosmology*. Basel: Gordon and Breach Science Publishers, S.A.
- Hawking, S. and Mlodinow, L. 2011. *The Grand Design*. London: Transworld Publishers.
- Hobson, A. 2013. “There are no particles, there are only fields”, *American Journal of Physics*, 81 (3): 211.
- Hobson, A. 2005. “Electrons as field quanta: A better way to teach quantum physics in introductory general physics courses”, *American Journal of Physics*, 73 (7): 630-634.
- Hubert, M, and Romano, D. 2018. *The Wave-Function as a Multi-Field*. arXiv 1710.03260. Retrieved 24th December 2022.
- Hughes, I.S. 1985. *Elementary Particles*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Jones, G.T. 2002. “The uncertainty principle, virtual particles and real forces”, *Physics Education*, 37 (3): 223-233.
- Joshi, N.V. 2016. “The Nature, Origin and Propagation of the Electric Field: A New Insight to Fundamental Physics”, *Journal of Modern Physics*, 7: 1132-1137.
- Kraus, J.D., 1984. *Electromagnetics*, Singapore: McGraw-Hill Book Co.
- Kuhlmann, M. 2018. “Quantum Field Theory”, In E.N. Zalta (ed.), *The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy* (Winter 2018 Edition). Retrieved 4th January 2020 from the World Wide Web: <https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/win2018/entries/quantum-field-theory/>

Leggett, A.J., and Garg, A. (1985). "Quantum Mechanics versus Macroscopic Realism: Is the Flux There when Nobody Looks?" *Physical Review Letters* 54 (9).

Mahdi, J.N. 2014. "On the nature of electric charge", *International Journal of Physical Sciences* 9 (4): 54-60.

McDonald, K.T. 2018. "Does Destructive Interference Destroy Energy?" Retrieved 8th September 2022 from the World Wide Web: <https://kirkmcd.princeton.edu>

Sebens, C.T. 2019a. *Particles, Fields, and the Measurement of Electron Spin*. arXiv: 2007:00619v2. Retrieved 1st July 2022.

Spiegel, M.R. 1987. *Theoretical Mechanics*. Singapore: McGraw-Hill Book Inc.

